

DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING BUSINESS ACTIVITY IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract.

The article deals with the ways of improving business activities in the development of the economy, providing employment at the expense of creating new jobs, improving people's well-being.

Key words.

economy, efficiency, entrepreneurship, business, environment, entrepreneurial activity, foreign investment, economic mechanism, investment system.

In our republic, the direction of small business is characterized by the fact that it has developed at a slower pace than neighboring countries, and the indicators related to the sector are noticeable, but the level of sustainable development of small business enterprises is being ensured slowly. The increase in the share of small enterprises among the leading sectors and sectors of the economy began to emerge as a solid foundation for economic growth and social stability.

Therefore, introduction of systematic democratic market reforms, further deepening of economic liberalization processes, consistent implementation of structural changes in many sectors, continuation of modernization and diversification processes are the main factors of Uzbekistan's success. The continuous growth of the country's gross domestic product is not due to the traditional raw materials industries or the favorable conditions in the world market, the high prices of some raw materials and materials, but on the contrary, it is provided due to the rapid and priority development of the production of competitive finished products and modern service industries.

As we know, some areas of business activity are one of the main sectors of the economy of our republic. Because many areas of business activity are fundamentally different from other areas and sectors with their added value creation, their role in meeting the needs of the population, and their high-level

production locomotive. The development of entrepreneurship leads to the development of the national economy at a steady pace. Processing of all resources in business activities, production of new products from them, diversification processes are improved due to increase in assortment and nomenclature.

At the same time, in the development of the economy entrepreneurship effective management of activities as an important indicator of social relations applies to all aspects of social life. In other words, management establishes an agreement between all participants and elements of production, regulates the content and norms of the relations that have arisen, and contributes to finding effective ways of using resources. This activity is constantly improving and developing.

From this point of view, it is important to apply modern management principles in small business and entrepreneurial activity and to achieve high development rates based on it.

Business management activities are carried out on the basis of certain principles. These principles, firstly, establish agreements between production participants, and secondly, prevent errors that may occur and increase the efficiency of management work.

Modern science and management practices accept the following principles of enterprise management as the most basic: scientificity, systematicity and complexity, individual management and collegiality, order and justice, material and moral stimulation of employees, thrift and efficiency, initiative and corporate spirit, authority and responsibility.

Until now, in the development of business activities a number of principles of production organization and management are being used. The principles change over time and adapt to the existing conditions. Based on the requirements of modernization of the economy, it is necessary to develop new and improved principles in this direction, which will determine the country's prospects.

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